

**RECENT ADVANCES IN ARAMID FIBER
AND COMPOSITE TECHNOLOGY**

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ABSTRACT

A new para-aramid fiber has been developed which has a modulus of elasticity up to 40% greater than that of previous high modulus p-aramid fibers together with low equilibrium moisture content. This fiber has a very high level of crystalline order and several unique structural features which are responsible for its improved property levels. Initial tests show the fiber may be particularly well suited for composite applications. This paper focuses on the key properties and structural characteristics of this fiber, the results of preliminary composite evaluations in an epoxy matrix, and some future developments that may be anticipated for p-aramids for advanced composite applications.

INTRODUCTION

The discovery of liquid crystalline solutions of extended chain aromatic polyamides has resulted in a family of high performance aramid fibers with unique combinations of engineering properties. Such fibers made from the para-aramid poly-para phenylene terephthalamide (PPD-T) have been available commercially since the early 1970's under the Du Pont trademark Kevlar* aramid and include "Kevlar" 29 used for ballistics, ropes and protective apparel, and the higher modulus "Kevlar" 49 used

*Du Pont registered trademark

extensively as an organic matrix reinforcement. Using unique technology, Du Pont has now developed a new p-aramid fiber called "Kevlar" 149 with a different combination of properties including inherent low moisture pickup and a modulus of elasticity up to 40% greater than that of previous high modulus p-aramid fibers. This paper first describes the properties of this new fiber, discusses its structural features and their relation to properties, presents initial results on performance in epoxy matrix composites, and concludes with some brief comments on other developments and future thrusts for p-aramids.

PROPERTIES

Bare Fiber

Table 1 summarizes the properties of dry twisted yarns of "Kevlar" 149 in comparison with other p-aramids. Because of its more highly ordered crystalline structure, this fiber exhibits a significantly higher modulus of elasticity than previous p-aramid fibers. The yarn has an initial modulus (measured at 20% of ultimate strength) of 146 GPa (21.3 Mpsi) while the secant modulus between 0 and 1% strain is 160 GPa (23.2 Mpsi). The stress-strain curve is characterized by a slight stiffening or increasing modulus with strain, but is highly elastic with very low hysteresis on cycling, recovering, for instance, 96% of input strain energy when unloaded from 60% of ultimate. In contrast, "Kevlar" 49 has a more nearly linear stress-strain curve and recovers about 91% of input strain energy when unloaded from the same stress. The tensile strength of the new yarn is 2400 MPa (350 Kpsi) and the elongation 1.5% compared with 2900 MPa (420 Kpsi) and 2.4% for "Kevlar" 49.

TABLE 1
Dry Twisted Fiber (Yarn) Properties
(1267 dtex, 95 tpm)

		<u>"Kevlar" 149 Aramid</u>	<u>"Kevlar" 49 Aramid</u>	<u>"Kevlar" 29 Aramid</u>
Initial Modulus,	GPa	146	114	62
Secant Modulus to 1% Elongation,	GPa	160	117	62
Tensile Strength,	MPa	2410	2900	2900
Elongation,	%	1.4-1.5	2.4	3.8
Density,	g/cm ³	1.47	1.44	1.44
Moisture Regain, (72°F, 55% RH)	%	1.0-1.2	4.3	4.8

Impregnated Fiber

When fiber tensile properties are measured using the epoxy impregnated strand test (ASTM-D2343-67), higher levels are obtained (Table 2). The tensile modulus is 180 GPa (26 Mpsi) measured between 0.2-0.6% strain, increasing to 186 GPa (27 Mpsi) between 0.4-0.8% strain. This is 40% higher than that of previous high modulus p-aramids and nearly equivalent to the specific modulus of high tensile strength (HT) graphites such as AS-4. The strand tensile strength averages over 3450 MPa (500 Kpsi) with 1.8-1.9% elongation. This tensile strength is only 5-10% lower than for "Kevlar" 49 and is higher than would be expected based on unimpregnated yarn property comparisons. The impregnated strand stress-strain curves are shown in Figure 1.

TABLE 2
Epoxy Impregnated Strand Tensile Properties
(ASTM - D2343-67)

		"Kevlar" 149 Aramid	"Kevlar" 49 Aramid	E-Glass	HT Graphite
Tensile Modulus, (0.2-0.6% strain)	GPa	172-180	124-131	69	227
Specific Tensile Modulus,	km	12.2	9.0	2.76	13.3
Tensile Strength,	MPa	3450	3620	2410	3585
Specific Tensile Strength,	km	240	256	99	203
Strain to Failure, %		1.8-1.9	2.9	3.5	1.53

Figure 1. Strand Tensile Stress-Strain Curves

Other

Several other properties are also unique. The fiber is more compact with a 2% higher density than "Kevlar" 49 and an equilibrium moisture content of about 1% at 55% RH, 25°C, about a quarter that of "Kevlar" 49. This lower moisture pickup can be important in composite applications for ease of processing and stability of electrical properties, for instance. The yarn has a linear creep rate vs. log (time) of only 0.011% per 10X time change (load = 50% of ultimate), about the same as measured for drawn carbon steel wire. This compares with 0.017% per 10X time change for "Kevlar" 49 and 0.050% for "Kevlar" 29 at the same load. Property retention at elevated temperatures is comparable to other p-aramids and strength retention is 80% after heat aging 3 hours at 240°C in air. It also appears from a high spot test that this yarn has significantly better hydrolytic stability than "Kevlar" 49.

STRUCTURE-PROPERTY RELATIONS

Para-aramids are highly crystalline materials [1,2]. In the fiber, the molecules have an orientation nearly parallel to the fiber axis and are aligned in parallel hydrogen bonded sheets with a well defined radial orientation as shown in Figure 2 [3,4], referred to as lateral crystalline order. In previous commercially available p-aramid fibers spun from liquid crystal solutions, there appears to be a small amount of regular molecular disorientation, called axial banding or pleating of the hydrogen bonded sheets also shown in Figure 2 [5]. The fibrillar nature of para-aramid fibers is believed to result from the coagulation and solidification of oriented liquid crystal domains during the spinning process. This spinning process can also result in a skin-core morphology which has been observed many times [6].

Figure 2. Fiber Structure - "Kevlar" 49 Aramid

"Kevlar" 149 has a higher level of crystalline order than other p-aramid fibers as illustrated by a study of wide angle x-ray parameters from two major peaks at 20 and 23 degrees (Table 3). Crystallinity index, determined from peak height, is a rough measure of extent of crystalline character and is significantly higher for "Kevlar" 149. Likewise, crystallite size, determined from the breadth of the peaks, is higher in all dimensions. On the (110) and (200) lattice planes, the apparent crystallite size is 111Å and 75Å, respectively, vs. 56Å and 51Å for "Kevlar" 49, indicating the frequency of lateral defects or crystalline disorder is significantly less for the new fiber.

The X-ray orientation angle, however, is the same for this new fiber as for "Kevlar" 49, providing evidence that orientation is not the only factor determining modulus. A paracrystalline model appears applicable to rigid rod-like molecules. This model envisions a single-phase crystalline structure characterized by cumulative long-range lattice distortions. A paracrystalline distortion parameter, g_{II} , may be calculated by examining the meridional x-ray trace of a number of yarns and this parameter is found to correlate strongly with modulus [2]. Theoretical calculations based on perfect alignment and crystal order predict a modulus potential of about 220 GPa (32 Mpsi) while moduli up to 207 GPa (30 Mpsi) have been measured on experimental samples. Dimensions of the orthorhombic unit cell also are larger for "Kevlar" 149.

TABLE 3
X-Ray Parameters for P-Aramid Fibers

	"Kevlar" 149 Aramid	"Kevlar" 49 Aramid	"Kevlar" 29 Aramid
Crystallinity Index	75	53	43
Apparent Crystallite Size (110) ($2\theta=20^\circ$), Angstroms	111	56	46
(200) ($2\theta=23^\circ$), Angstroms	75	51	45
Orientation Angle, °	8-10	8-10	16
Paracrystallinity Disorder Parameter, g_{II} , %	1.7	2.1	2.4
Unit Cell Dimensions, Anstroms			
a	7.88	7.73	7.85
b	5.18	5.18	5.15
c	12.94	12.82	12.80

Optical and scanning electron microscopy also reveal the absence of the regular pleat structure found in previous p-aramids [7]. Transverse fiber features revealed by caustic etching followed by fiber fracture [8],

show a fracture surface that appears to have a fine grained radial structure without definable microfibrils or pleats and no clear skin-core gradient (Figure 3a). With "Kevlar" 49 (Figure 3b), fracture appears to occur in the pleated region in the core of the fiber, while the skin has a more jagged fracture surface. The filaments themselves are round as they are for other p-aramids, but may show some fissures in the surface closely paralleling but at a slight angle to the fiber axis. These do not appear to influence mechanical properties, including fatigue resistance.

Figure 3a. Fracture of Caustic Etched Filament of "Kevlar" 149 Aramid

COMPOSITE PROPERTIES

Unidirectional epoxy matrix composite properties are shown in Table 4. Tensile strengths are consistent with expectations based on strand strength comparisons but higher than would be expected based on dry yarn strength. The slight stiffening found in the yarn and strand stress-strain curves (Figure 1) is also present for the unidirectional composites. The modulus measured between 0.2-0.5% strain shows a 35-40% increase, and the same strand-to-composite modulus translation efficiency as "Kevlar" 49. The modulus increase is less (15-20%) if measured between 0 and 0.2% strain due to the nonlinear stress-strain relation.

Compressive strength is not changed versus previous p-aramids and the compressive modulus increase is comparable to that in tension measured between 0-0.2% strain. This is to be expected since the compressive

Figure 3b. Fracture of Caustic Etched Filament of "Kevlar" 49 Aramid

modulus must be measured at low strain before yielding occurs starting about 0.3% strain. The compressive stress-strain curve appears similar to previous p-aramids in that it shows a yielding followed by plastic deformation with good energy absorbing properties. Flexural strength is equivalent to "Kevlar" 49 and flexural modulus improvement is again reflective of the 0-0.2% portion of the stress-strain curve (15-20% increase).

Interlaminar shear strengths show similar results to "Kevlar" 49, implying equivalent fiber-resin adhesion while longitudinal thermal expansion coefficient was found to be near zero but very slightly positive in contrast to the slightly negative value for unidirectional composites of "Kevlar" 49. To assess time dependent behavior, unidirectional laminates were tension-tension fatigue tested between 110-1100 MPa stress and the excellent performance of "Kevlar" 49/epoxy duplicated.

Intensive efforts are underway to expand the data base for both unidirectional and fabric composites, including hybrid composites with carbon.

TABLE 4
Unidirectional Composite Properties
60% Fiber, 0° Direction

		"Kevlar" 149 Aramid	"Kevlar" 49 Aramid	"ThorneI" 300 Graphite
Tensile Strength,	MPa	1450	1500	1420
Tensile Modulus,	GPa	107	79	133
% Conversion		99	99	97
Strain-to-Failure,	%	1.33	1.71	0.90
Compressive Strength,	MPa	193	234	-
Compressive Modulus,	GPa	73	66	-
Flexural Strength,	MPa	634	655	1192
Flexural Modulus,	GPa	79	67	116
Interlaminar Shear Strength,	MPa	57	59	70
Thermal Exp. Coeff.,	10^{-6} m/m°C	+0.37	-2.33	-

- Epon 828 epoxy cured with NMA/BDMA

APPLICATIONS

"Kevlar" 149 appears well suited for composite applications. The high modulus, coupled with damage tolerance inherent to organic fibers, is expected to be useful in hybrid composites with carbon where the high modulus will give better strain compatibility and load sharing. New engineering design options also appear possible in applications such as stiffness critical helicopter components, low expansion metal lined pressure vessels, printed wiring boards with engineered thermal expansion properties, electrical insulators, space structures and sporting goods. Other potential uses include fiber optic cable reinforcement, low stretch antenna guy lines, low creep timing and drive belts, low expansion hoses and even large tether lines to moor tension leg oil production platforms.

An example of a demonstrated performance advantage is that of a filament wound metal lined pressure vessel with low volumetric expansion on pressure cycling. Several 25.4 cm diameter aluminum lined pressure bottles were wound and pressurized 200 times to 22.8 MPa (3300 psi), which was 35% of burst pressure. The volumetric expansion using "Kevlar" 149 was reduced 10-15% compared to "Kevlar" 49 while maintaining nearly equal burst strength using a special fiber surface treatment. Since fatigue of the metal liner is the usual failure mechanism, reduced liner stress is expected to result in a major increase in the fatigue life of the vessel (estimated at 10X) based on the metal Stress-Cycles-to-Failure (S-N) curve. This will be the subject of a separate paper in the future.

FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Para-aramid fiber technology will continue to advance toward achieving tensile strength closer to theoretical, increasing chemical and hydrolytic stability, reducing moisture pick-up, and developing new product forms tailored for specific engineering needs.

Important new products are short fiber reinforced thermoset and thermoplastic resins which achieve outstanding resistance to abrasion and wear. Additionally, short fiber forms are gaining importance in elastomer reinforcement, adhesives and sealants, and in cement and concrete. New processing technologies based on thermoplastic matrix systems are being developed to lower composite fabrication costs which will be applied, for instance, in land transportation systems. Finally, better understanding of failure mechanisms and tailored fiber-matrix interfaces are leading to structures with enhanced toughness and crashworthiness in addition to high strength and stiffness.

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